

The Next-Generation Adaptive Optics Facility for Gemini North

Gaetano Sivo (NSF's NOIRLab), Julia Scharwächter (NSF's NOIRLab), and Suresh Sivanandam (University of Toronto)

Adaptive optics (AO) has been used for more than two decades at major observatories to obtain high-spatial-resolution observations from the ground. The basic principle of AO involves correcting the wavefront disturbances induced by Earth's atmosphere in real time using deformable mirrors. The Gemini North Adaptive Optics (GNAO) project will provide the Gemini North telescope with a state-of-the-art AO facility for survey, time-domain, and general-purpose science in the era of Vera C. Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) and *James Webb Space Telescope (JWST)* operations. GNAO is supported by the Gemini in the Era of Multi-Messenger Astronomy (GEMMA) program funded by NSF to advance the leadership role of the Gemini telescopes in high-resolution, time-domain, and

multi-messenger astronomy. By building on the legacy of Gemini Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics System (GeMS) at Gemini South, the GNAO project aims primarily at revitalizing the Gemini North AO capabilities with a flexible queue-operated facility. This will take full advantage of Maunakea's outstanding characteristics as a premier site for high-angular-resolution observations from the ground.

GNAO is expected to replace the aging single-conjugate AO facility ALTAIR on the AO port of the Gemini North telescope. The GNAO design will be optimized to feed the Gemini InfraRed Multi-Object Spectrograph (GIRMOS), an innovative near-infrared imager and multiplexed integral field unit (IFU) spectrograph [1] developed by a Canadian

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the primary GNAO-enabled instrument modes. GNAO will provide a baseline science wavelength coverage in the NIR reaching down to 0.83 μm.

Figure 2. GNAO optical schematic, including on-sky configuration, conjugated atmospheric layers and stylized deformable mirror, wavefront sensor, real time controller, and feedback loop. Also shown are laser guide star configurations and natural guide stars. *Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard*

consortium (P.I. Sivanandam, University of Toronto) in close collaboration with the GNAO team. While GIRMOS is the primary driver for defining the capabilities of GNAO, the new AO system will be available as a general facility for backend instruments operable with GNAO's $f/32$ output beam in the 0.83 to 2.5 μm wavelength range. Among the current Gemini North facility instruments, the optical workhorse instrument Gemini Multi-Object Spectrograph (GMOS) will be able to take advantage of the GNAO-corrected beam at the red end of the GMOS wavelength coverage.

The GNAO project includes the development of a new laser guide star facility, which will consist of four side-launched laser beams supporting the two primary AO modes of GNAO as well as a wide-field mode providing improved image quality over natural seeing for a 2' circular field of view and a narrow-field mode providing near diffraction-limited performance over a 20" \times 20" square field of view. The GNAO wide-field mode will enable GIRMOS's multi-IFU configuration in which the science beam to each individual IFU will be additionally corrected using multi-object AO within GIRMOS. The GNAO narrow-field mode will feed the GIRMOS-tiled IFU configuration in which all IFUs are combined into a 'super-IFU' in the center of the field. The GIRMOS imager will have a 85" \times 85" square field of view and can be operated with either the GNAO narrow-field or wide-field correction at a fixed plate scale, depending on the angular resolution and field size required for specific science goals.

Imaging	FoV	<i>K</i> -band (2.2 μ m) Performance	<i>H</i> -band (1.65 μ m) Performance	<i>J</i> -band (1.25 μ m) Performance
GNAO WFM (GLAO) 60% sky coverage	85" \times 85"	120 mas FWHM	150 mas FWHM	200 mas FWHM
GNAO NFM (LTAO) 60% sky coverage	20" \times 20"	SR 35%	SR 20%	SR 10%
GNAO on- axis (LTAO) 12 mag <i>R</i> -band limit	On-axis	SR 60%	SR 45%	SR 25%
Detector	HAWAII-4RG 4k \times 4k			
Plate Scale	0.021"			
Wavelength (μ m)	0.83 – 2.4			

Table 1: GIRMOS Imager characteristics and Image Quality (SR: Strehl Ratio) performance requirements in *J*, *H* and *K*-bands.

Spectroscopy			
Wavelength (μ m)	0.95–2.4	# of IFS	Up to 4
Spectral Resolving Power	3000 and 8000	Spectral Bands	0.95–1.35, 1.25–1.8, 1.63–2.35 μ m for <i>R</i> -3000 1.194–1.35, 1.5–1.706, 2.11–2.379 μ m for <i>R</i> -8000
FoV for MOAO arms	2' Patrol field		
IFS FoV (100% coverage)	1.0" \times 1.0" 2.0" \times 2.0" 4.0" \times 4.0"	Spaxel Sampling	0.025" 0.05" 0.1"
Single Object IFS FoV (Tiled mode)	2.0" \times 2.0" 4.0" \times 4.0" 8.0" \times 8.0"	Spaxel Sampling	0.025" 0.05" 0.1"
Throughput	35%	Detectors	4 \times HAWAII-2RG 2k \times 2k
GNAO+GIRMOS AO Image quality	50% EE in 0.05" in <i>H</i> band (LTAO mode) 50% EE in 0.1" in <i>H</i> band (MOAO mode) 50% EE in 0.4" in <i>H</i> band (GLAO mode)		

Table 2: GIRMOS spectroscopic characteristics and image quality performance requirements.

The GNAO project also includes the development of the following:

- The Adaptive Optics Bench, including the low-order natural guide star wavefront sensor, the high-order laser guide star wavefront sensor, and the fast-moving active element to correct for the aberrations induced by the atmosphere
- The Real Time Controller to compute and apply in real time the correction to the deformable mirrors
- The System Controller, including the operational software and AO software tools to calibrate and optimize the system and the logical sequencing of the observations

Figure 3: Science Case categories enabled with GNAO+GIRMOS
Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard

The design of the new AO facility for Gemini North is driven by a broad range of science cases, ranging from Solar System to extragalactic science. The overall science drivers include science cases developed by both the GNAO and GIRMOS science teams.

High-resolution facility for multi-messenger events

The example of the famous 2017 gravitational wave event GW170817 has demonstrated the power of multi-messenger astronomy as an important driver of astrophysical discoveries. GW170817 was the first gravitational wave event detected with an electromagnetic counterpart through a major world-wide observing campaign [2]. The gravitational wave signal together with the subsequent short gamma-ray burst (GRB) and follow-up detections across the electromagnetic spectrum have provided unprecedented insights into the physics of neutron star mergers, including their association with short GRBs as well as kilonova emission from radioactive decay during the synthesis of heavy elements. Characterizing the kilonova emission after a short GRB is a high-priority science driver for the GNAO narrow field mode, where high angular resolution will improve the detection of the transient against the background host galaxy light. As a queue-operated facility, GNAO is being developed to offer a rapid response mode to support this science case and early follow-up of other targets of opportunity, such as Solar System transients or new, unknown transients discovered with Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time.

Powerful capabilities for survey science

GNAO, in conjunction with GIRMOS, will provide powerful capabilities for spectroscopic surveys at high angular resolution. The multiplexing capabilities offered by the GIRMOS spectroscopic modes will be complementary to many aspects of galactic and extragalactic research conducted with the *JWST*. The GIRMOS spectroscopic modes are well suited to study targets such as star clusters, galaxy nuclei and supermassive black holes, lensed galaxies, and in the study of galaxy evolution from low to high redshift. Two of the primary science drivers for GIRMOS are a survey of galaxies between redshifts of 0.7 and 2.7 and a survey of globular clusters, taking advantage of the multi-IFU and tiled-IFU configurations, respectively. The galaxy survey will provide unprecedented sample sizes of high-angular-resolution IFU data to study the role of mergers, star formation, and feedback

processes in the build-up of galaxy mass around redshift 2. Globular clusters are candidates for hosting intermediate-mass black holes, which are expected to exist in the mass range between stellar-mass and supermassive black holes but have remained difficult to detect. The spatially resolved spectroscopy obtained with the GIRMOS globular cluster survey will provide new opportunities to systematically search for observational signatures of the much sought-after intermediate-mass black holes.

Flexibility for Solar System science and multi-epoch studies

AO-assisted observations from ground-based telescopes have traditionally been an important technique for advancing our knowledge of the Solar System. Ground-based observations play a major part in studying the atmospheres of the giant planets (e.g., wind shear, convection, seasonal variations) or variable phenomena on their moons, such as the volcanic activity on Io [3]. Science cases focusing on multi-epoch observations to monitor Solar System objects or to characterize the time evolution of protostellar jets and outflows at high angular resolution require an AO facility that is available on a virtually nightly basis. By supporting Solar System studies through a non-sidereal tracking option and by operating as a queue-scheduled facility, GNAO will provide exciting new opportunities for such high-angular-resolution work in the time domain within and beyond the Solar System.

The GNAO project is fully managed in-house under the leadership of Gaetano Sivo (Principal Investigator), Manuel Lazo (Project Manager), Julia Scharwächter (Project Scientist), Stephen Goodsell (Project Director), William Rambold (Lead Systems engineer), and Jennifer Lotz (Gemini Director). The Laser Guide Star Facility is designed and built in-house except for the Laser Launch Telescopes that are contracted out to Officina Stellare in Vicenza (Italy). The Real Time Controller is developed by Herzberg Astronomy and Astrophysics in Victoria (Canada). The Adaptive Optics Bench is currently under a call for tenders / bid selection process. The project timeline currently foresees first light of GNAO during the first quarter of 2028.

References:

- [1] Sivanandam, S., et al. 2020, *Proc. SPIE*, 11447, 114471A
- [2] Abbott, B. P., et al. 2017, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 119, 161101
- [3] de Kleer, K., et al. 2019, *AJ*, 158, 29